

Report – Dissemination and Training Activities of the Italian National Chapter of CoARA

Creator: Italian National Chapter

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Overview

Between September 2023 and July 2025, the Italian National Chapter of CoARA organized one in-person event and three online training seminars aimed at fostering awareness and dialogue around key themes of research assessment reform. These events were designed to engage researchers, academic policy makers, and professionals involved in research evaluation and communication, in line with CoARA's principles of openness, transparency, and inclusivity.

1. Training event: “Opening science. Towards a reform of the research assessment system”

Date: January 11th, 2024

Address: Aula Magna of the University of Pisa

Palazzo della Sapienza, via Curtatone e Montanara, Pisa

Duration: 3,5 hrs

Scope: To introduce the elements of the reform; to introduce elements of research assessment in Horizon Europe program; to make it clear how open science and research evaluation reform are connected; and to introduce Open Science courses targeted to PhD in the 4 RPOs involved.

Targets: PhD students of the Scuola Normale Superiore, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, University of Pisa, National Research Council of Italy (CNR - Pisa)

Organized by: Associazione Italiana per la promozione della Scienza aperta (AISA) CNR - Area della ricerca di Pisa Scuola Normale Superiore Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna University of Pisa CoARA Italian National Chapter

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10565207>

Video: <https://garr.tv/w/heumFMEFpEUxQPNPTCXNkn>

2. Seminar: “The European Commission’s Action Plan for Research Assessment Reform”

Date: September 25, 2024

Speaker: Silvia Bottaro (Legal and Policy Officer, DG Research and Innovation, European Commission)

Introduced by: Francesca Di Donato (CNR) and Francesca Masini (University of Bologna), Co-Chairs of the Italian National Chapter

Moderator: Federica Cappelluti (Politecnico di Torino)

Format: Online

Participants registered: 148

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13840168>

This seminar provided an overview of the European Commission's commitments within the CoARA framework, highlighting the ten key actions outlined in the official Action Plan. Silvia Bottaro discussed the strategic role of Open Science and the Commission's roadmap for implementing reform across member states.

3. Seminar: "New Editorial and Peer Review Models Inspired by Open Science Principles"

Date: June 18, 2025

Speakers:

- Timothy Behrens & Alessio Bolognesi (eLife)
- Marta Arzarello (University of Ferrara)
- Maria Chiara Pievatolo (University of Pisa)

Moderator: Federica Cappelluti (Politecnico di Torino)

Format: Online

Participants registered: 107

Slides: [10.5281/zenodo.17220501](https://zenodo.org/record/17220501/files/10.5281)

This event explored innovative publishing and peer review models across disciplines, including life sciences, archaeology, and political philosophy. The speakers presented concrete alternatives to traditional systems, such as Peer Community In Archaeology and open peer review practices, and discussed the challenges posed by centralized evaluation systems.

4. Seminar: "Open Resources for Research Monitoring and Evaluation"

Date: July 9, 2025

Speakers:

- Paola Galimberti (University of Milan)
- Silvio Peroni (University of Bologna)

Moderator: Federica Cappelluti (Politecnico di Torino)

Format: Online

Participants registered: 135

Slides: [10.5281/zenodo.17220580](https://zenodo.org/record/17220580/files/10.5281)

This seminar, held in Italian, focused on the use of open data and infrastructures for research evaluation. Paola Galimberti shared institutional experiences in transitioning to open sources for internal and external assessment, while Silvio Peroni introduced OpenCitations as a key infrastructure supporting bibliographic transparency and openness.

Conclusion

These seminars contributed to the dissemination of CoARA's principles and fostered a national dialogue on reforming research assessment practices. The diversity of topics and speakers ensured a multidisciplinary approach, and the open format encouraged broad participation and engagement.

In total, the four CoARA seminars saw participation from individuals affiliated with 75 different institutions, estimated based on unique email domains.

A list of events in which CoARA NC members took part is also available on the Italian NC website: <https://www.coara-italia.it/gli-eventi/>